

Factors Influencing the Individual Donor's Intention to Donate to Donation-Based Crowdfunding Campaigns: An Empirical Study Using the UTAUT Model

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Abstract

Purpose – The objective of this research is to investigate the donor's behaviour by applying the UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology) and to propose a research pattern that predicts the individual's donor intentions to donate towards donation-based crowdfunding campaigns in India.

Design/Methodology/Approach – The Empirical data gathered through an online survey. The facts gathered from actual and potential donors who likely to take part in online philanthropy was analysed using PLS-SEM Model.

Findings – The data shows that donor's intentions to contribute to donation-based crowdfunding campaigns are highly influenced by performance expectations, social influence and a sense of trust. The effect of performance expectations and effort expectations have an adverse effect on donors' intentions.

Research limitations/implications – The focal point of the present investigation is on the potential donors. In the future scope of research, it will be evident if there are distinctions with respect to the real donors. This study examines the implications for potential donor's intentions to donate towards donation-based crowdfunding campaigns.

Practical implications – The study provides suggestions for crowdfunding platforms on how to improve their functions and attract new donors to campaigns and it gives campaign creators insight into the elements that funders take in to account and how to enhance donor's willingness to make monetary donation on platforms for charitable crowdfunding and the campaign's total success rate, which gives a win-win approach to all related parties.

Originality/value – The conclusions of this study provide academics, researchers, crowdfunding platforms and campaign creators with a more thorough understanding of the factors that drive individual donor donations. This study further expands the UTAUT in the context of donation crowdfunding, which improves its effectiveness in explaining the behavioural intentions of donors. These theories may be an important part of future information systems and related behavioural science research.

Keywords: - Donation based Crowdfunding, Donor's Intention, Donation Factors, Charitable Campaigns, UTUAT Model, India.

JEL Classification: C91, G2, M14, L31.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, India's digital sector (the Internet) has experienced tremendous growth as users have access to an increasing number of digital services (Theerthaana Panneer, 2021)(Kumra et al., 2021). The Consultation Paper states that, "crowdfunding is the solicitation of funds (generally in small amounts) from multiple investors through a web-based platform or social networking site for a specific project, business venture or social cause." Based on the returns, crowdfunding can be divided into four different types: reward, lending, and equity, and donation-based crowdfunding (Sentanoe & Oktavia, 2022).

Crowdfunding, particularly donation-based crowdfunding, is one among the digital services that is becoming more popular in India (Maleki & Hosseini, 2020). It is a brand new developing online funding for philanthropically activities by

using social media, enables the use of social media by project fundraisers and cutting edge payment technologies (Mansyur & Ali, 2022).

With the aid of this concept, the fundraiser can solicit money from the "crowd" without having to deal with the complicated requirements that traditional funding methods such as bank loans require which are in principle, more widely available (Sayedi & Baghaie, 2018).

Donation is the voluntary act of supporting a cause or a person's effort without expecting anything in return (Behl & Dutta, 2020). It also includes advocating for improvements in religion, education or any other socially positively useful endeavours. Individuals are not directly benefited by their donation in any way. It implies that donors motivation for using the service may not be to get the rewards (Baber, 2019).

Web-based services offer an expanding chance to locate communities of people who support a business's or organisation's purpose or core values. Social media can assist non-profit organisations in connecting with a broader audience and building a stronger donor base (Kusumarani & Zo, 2019).

The purpose of the research is to assess the impact of individual donor's intentions on donation-based crowd funding by using social media platforms and technology or UTAUT, has a light of the backdrop. Through the use of social media, organisations are now able to influence people's intentions to donate by appealing to their willingness to use technology (UTAUT) (Tri Kurniawati et al., 2021)(Sulaeman & Ninglasari, 2020b).

The study will be extremely significant for the academic and business communities. Particularly, the present article offers service providers guidance on how to enhance and perfect their capabilities and offers crowdfunding donation fundraisers realistic suggestions on how to enhance the success rate (Efrat et al., 2019). The investigational findings give us better theoretical knowledge regarding the motivations behind people's intentions when it comes to academic crowdfunding donations.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The welfare of society is the main issues facing every government in any economy. Individuals and organisations will operate as the backbone to support towards welfare of society as a whole through charitable activities, corporate social responsibility and other initiatives that improve those who are struggling on both the economic and social levels (Tanaka & Voids, 2016).

Crowdfunding is a novel method of obtaining money for projects by exchanging rewards for donations or other financial resources over the Internet (Zhang et al., 2020). Traditional charity fundraising efforts are frequently restricted to particular populations and geographic areas, while donation based crowdfunding removes these limitations (Behl et al., 2020).

While the concept of crowdfunding has received a lot of practitioners and academic attention, existing research predominates (Baber, 2020). Academic researchers, business people, investors and decision makers are all becoming an escalating interested in the crowdfunding phenomenon (Sulaeman & Ninglasari, 2020a). Crowdfunding has been praised in the popular press as a practical substitute for established fundraising channels that may even be able to "save the economy." (Shneor & Munim, 2019)

Each recipient has the chance to influence donors to decide to give by presenting them with a relatable charity appeal. This method of fundraising clarifies the significance of the philanthropic request. Giving time, effort, and money (both monetary and non-monetary) to spread goodness to others without expecting anything in return is a significant portion of philanthropy. Which advance the nation's welfare, growth, and societal needs (Wang et al., 2019).

More study is required to confirm the findings for donation model as well as the primary emphasis of the investigation is on creators and platforms view. Regarding the contributors and their desire to utilize the service is minimum, the study is anticipated to offer additional insights on possible donors towards donation-based crowdfunding in India.

The most popular models in psychology, sociology, behavior and communications were considered at every stage of the literature review procedure (Mansyur & Ali, 2022) (Venkatesh et al., 2003), and UTAUT is among the most effective models for utilizing the recently produced technology (Alawadhi & Morris, 2008), which forecasts and explains how people consider the rate of adoption of new technology while taking action (Erjavec & Manfreda, 2022). With sense of trust as added explanatory variable, this research will use the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) as its research paradigm. UTAUT has been demonstrated to be successful in examining user acceptance and intention to utilize a technology product, it was chosen to serve as a model for the study (Venkatesh & Zhang, 2014). The study also further extends the UTAUT Model in the context of donation-based crowdfunding, which improves their robustness in explaining behavior intention. These theories may be important in future information system and behavioral sciences research.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research framework and hypothesis development

The objective of the research is to use empirical research to analyse the internal and external elements that influence donor's intentions for participating in donation crowdfunding campaigns. The research model is built using the UTAUT model from earlier studies.

Research design

Model of factors influences donor's intention towards contributions

3.2 Measures:

Considering the goal of the study, where measurements were developed using a literature review, the operational definitions of the constructs had to be made necessary changes in the view of Indian context. The survey aims to comprehend donor's behavioral intentions and opinions regarding the donation-based crowdfunding. Donor's behavior based on given factors towards donations may have a positive or negative influence towards DCF.

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT):

One of the most recent technology acceptance models created by (Venkatesh et al., 2016) UTAUT. It unifies the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Motivational Model (MM), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), Combination of TAM and TPB, Model of PC Utilization (MPTU), Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT), and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) are the eight most popular technology acceptance theories that it effectively integrates into a single theory (Venkatesh & Zhang, 2014). In explaining 70% of user variances, it has been demonstrated to be more successful than the others. Its four main structural components are performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions, serve as important direct determinants of the purpose of behaviorism and use behavior (Yeoh & Yin-fah, 2011). It was then developed by adding the one of additional component, namely sense of trust in studies of donation intentions. The inquiry was carried out to find out whether all the factors significantly influences the donors donating behavior.

Performance Expectancy (PE)

According to (Venkatesh et al., 2003) defined as "the degree to which an individual believes that using a system will help him or her to attain gains in job performance." Donation behavior under the circumstances of DCF campaigns might be driven by an intention to escape other people's contempt or to obtain praise and approval from others, to promote social connection and to recognize the importance of the moral and emotional advantages. Participating in philanthropic crowdfunding makes contributors feel good about themselves, which influences their willingness to take part. Based on prior study, PE is defined as the degree to which a person who supports a philanthropic initiative using a DCF platform thinks that doing so will enable them to attain individual fulfilment, social connection, social approval and a feeling of accomplishment.

Effort expectancy (EE)

According to (Venkatesh et al., 2003) defined as "the degree of ease associated with the use of a system." We presume that donor's intentions to donate are encouraged by the DCF platform's simplicity of use and the ease of the donation process.

Social influence (SI)

According to (Venkatesh et al., 2003) defined as “an individual’s perception of how important it is that others consider that he or she should use the new system.” Individual’s donations for giving to charity often stem from societal obligation, religious tradition and personal philosophy. The acceptance of personal social responsibility has a big impact on how donors behave. Individuals who have strong opinions about doing well for others are likely to be more generous. Individual acts of kindness are also influenced by the conduct of other people. The amount of each donation depends on how much everyone else donates.

Facilitating conditions (FC)

According to (Venkatesh et al., 2003) defined as “the degree to which an individual believes that an organizational and technical infrastructure exists to support the use of the system.” Previous research has proven that a variety of information sources and media representations of the project, including social media platforms, frequently lead to a better understanding of crowdfunding initiatives in relation to charitable efforts. We believe that a project's leading donor status, variety of project material, and social media project promotion activity all have a major influence on encouraging donor motivation.

The following hypothesis that we put forth:

UTAUT factors significantly influences the donor’s plan to take part in Donation based crowdfunding campaigns.

Sense of Trust (SOT)

One of the key components of a successful crowdfunding campaign has been shown to be trust since crowd sourcing for charitable causes gained popularity in the era of electronic commerce / online shopping. There are numerous types of trust for different crowd sourcing models which includes personal, professional and social institutions. In the present research, a supporter's sense of trust is defined as their level of confidence in the platform for crowd fund raising, the project and the initiators. Donor intention will be influenced by a crowdfunding platform's security, power and professionalism along with a crowd-funding project's dependability and management structure, the reliability of the project's originator and past similar experience.

Sense of trust significantly influences the donor’s desire to take part in Donation based crowdfunding campaigns.

IV. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

4.1 Instrument design

To ensure content validity, the survey items that will be used for measurement were created using scales taken from earlier research. To meet the goals of this research, every element of the questions is carefully examined. A brief summary of the research was given in the questionnaire's introduction to better understanding. To determine the questionnaire's face validity, whether the respondents can easily grasp the questions. Prior to distribution, the items were reviewed by subject matter experts in this field, and a pilot study involving 30 college students was done to improve readability.

Sl. No	Construct	Number of Items	Adopted Scale Reference
1	Performance Expectancy (PE)	4	(Chong et al., 2012) (Theerthaana Panneer, 2021) (Ya, Zheng , Li, Tong-Liang He, Yi-Ran Song, 2017) (Kim & Hall, 2020)
2	Effort expectancy (EE)	4	
3	Social influence (SI)	4	
4	Facilitating conditions (FC)	3	
5	Sense of trust (SOT)	4	
6	Donor’s intention to participate in DCF- (IP- DBCF)	4	

4.2 Data Collection characteristics

The research is focused on donation-based crowdfunding along with the perspective of donors, the sample units selected for this research are actual donors and potential donors who have empathy for other people's causes and needs, who like to help and who are willing to contribute the donations financial for activities towards online philanthropy using donation-based crowdfunding model.

Data were gathered via an online survey method from several locations in Bengaluru, primarily the Central and South Zones, which represent the diverse population of India. Because it is difficult to estimate the precise population size of the donors who prefer to donate towards donation-based models, the study used a non-probability-based convenience and purposive sampling methods.

The survey was sent to mail and distributed to both private and public groups on social networking platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and What's Up. The data was collected from June 2023 to August 2023 using a well-structured with

closed ended questionnaire. 245 submission from the respondents were received; however, only 207 responses that met the criteria were carefully selected for investigation, which satisfying the acceptance rate. Additionally, the sample size complies with the general guidelines and rules for modelling structural equation and sample size would be ten times more than the instrument's maximum allowed for a given measurement item (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2016).

V. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

Prior the model was put into the test. The normality test was performed on the data using the Shapiro-Wilk test, which showed a significant result, Additionally, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test Sphericity tests, which showed positive sample adequacy (KMO: 0.863; Bartlett's test: significant at 0.00), were used to solidify the sampling adequacy. Partial Least Squares (PLS) was chosen to assess the study model as it has a numerous of advantages.

Respondent characteristics

Characteristics	Respondents (n=207)	
	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	86	41.5
Female	121	58.5
Age		
21-30	67	32.3
31-40	88	42.5
41-50	31	14.9
51-60	10	4.8
60 & above	11	5.5
Education		
Diploma	6	2.8
Graduate	90	43.4
Post Graduate	92	44.4
Professional Degree	10	4.8
PhD	9	4.6
Occupation		
Private Employee	162	78.2
Government Employee	28	13.5
Self-Employment/ Business	17	8.3
Income		
0 to 5,00,000	134	64.7
5,00,001 to 10,00,000	24	11.5
10,00,001 to 15,00,000	45	21.9
15,00,001 & above	4	1.9

The internal consistency(reliability), convergent validity and discriminant validity of the model were assessed using a (PLS) algorithm using Smart PLS 4.0. To estimate the convergent and discriminant validity of the research constructs, an confirmatory factor analysis was used (Vong et al., 2014).

Confirmatory factor analysis results, Reliability and validity						
Construct	Items	Factor loadings	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Performance Expectancy (PE)	PE1	0.746	0.817	0.828	0.879	0.645
	PE2	0.835				
	PE3	0.806				
	PE4	0.821				
Effort expectancy (EE)	EE1	0.733	0.777	0.780	0.856	0.599
	EE2	0.777				
	EE3	0.796				
	EE4	0.788				
	SI1	0.782	0.827	0.832	0.885	0.659
	SI2	0.859				

Social influence (SI)	SI3	0.846	0.747	0.771	0.856	0.665
	SI4	0.755				
Facilitating conditions (FC)	FC1	0.726	0.833	0.840	0.889	0.667
	FC2	0.880				
	FC3	0.833				
Sense of trust (SOT)	SOT1	0.759	0.843	0.848	0.895	0.682
	SOT2	0.824				
	SOT3	0.855				
	SOT4	0.826				
Donor's intention to participate in DCF- (IP-DBCF)	IPDCF1	0.745	0.843	0.848	0.895	0.682
	IPDCF2	0.852				
	IPDCF3	0.846jj				
	IPDCF4	0.854				

Note: * All standard loadings are significant at $p < 0.001$ ".

'Composite reliability' is established by assessing the correlations between measurement items and their corresponding constructs. 'Cronbach's alpha' and 'Composite reliability' (CR) were calculated to test construct validity. It was found that every measurement item exceeded both Cronbach's alpha and CR minimum criterion of 0.7.

Convergent validity is established by assessing the value of the average variance extracted (AVE) and monitoring the outer loadings of factor loadings analysis. The value of AVE shows the degree which the indicators explain the variance of the construct, which is recommended to be more than 0.5 (J. F. Hair et al., 2013). Every construct's AVE value exceeded the suggested level. The outer loadings for each construct explain whether the indicators successfully captured the value that explains the construct. Outer loadings greater than 0.7 is considered to show convergent validity (J. Hair et al., 2017). All indicators in our results demonstrate that outer loading values are significantly higher than the recommended threshold (Fornell, C & Larcker, D, 1981).

Discriminant Analysis -Correlations of the constructs and the square root of AVE						
Construct	PE	EE	SI	FC	SOT	IP-DBCF
PE	0.816					
EE	0.440	0.826				
SI	0.490	0.508	0.803			
FC	0.374	0.489	0.526	0.774		
SOT	0.403	0.536	0.556	0.699	0.812	
IP-DBCF	0.610	0.533	0.458	0.458	0.470	0.817

The Fornell-Lacker criterion compares the average variance extracted (AVE)'s square root relative to the possible variable correlation. The reliability values indicate that each construct shares more variance with its associated measurement items or indicators than with the other model constructs (J. Hair et al., 2017). The AVE value of each construct is higher than its highest correlation with the remaining constructs (Sarstedt et al., 2021).

Hypothesized Path	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics	P values	Sig	Results
FC -> IPDCF	0.066	0.070	0.086	0.769	0.442	No	Rejected
PE -> IPDCF	0.185	0.190	0.083	2.241	0.025	Yes	Accepted
EE -> IPDCF	0.094	0.101	0.095	0.992	0.321	No	Rejected
SI -> IPDCF	0.217	0.213	0.103	2.097	0.036	Yes	Accepted
SOT -> IPDCF	0.263	0.261	0.080	3.290	0.001	Yes	Accepted

Note: p-value < 0.000 – significant at 1% level; p-value < 0.05 – significant at 5% level.

The PLS path coefficients are shown. For three of the pathways, the t-statistics value is found to be higher than 1.96. Performance expectancy, social influence and the intention of the donor to participate is significantly positively impacted by a sense of trust. Facilitating conditions and effort expectancy has an adverse effect on the donor intention to participate. The explanatory power (R Square) of Donation Intention is 0.6264, According to (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2013) is considered as a better explanatory power.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

One latent variable (the sense of trust) was introduced to the UTAUT model in this study in order to build a research model of behavior influencing factors and donor intention to donate. The six paths all passed the model test, which is efficient and all six hypotheses are proven when Smart PLS 4 is used to analyse the survey data. We draw the conclusion that in the model, the three latent variables are all strongly correlated with donors' intentions to support campaigns based on donation-based model.

Therefore, in order to encourage the public to contribute money to a charitable crowdfunding project, we recommend that the project's creators provide adequate project information and describe the project's background and content to increase participation. Multimedia, including stories, photographs, and videos, can aid with this. So that as time passes, more individuals become aware and learn about the initiative. Gaining some influential donors early on in the endeavour is crucial for inspiring others to give as well. To educate the public, foster their feeling of social responsibility and aid them in developing the habit of giving through the internet. The crowd-funding platform's functionality and visual design should be continually enhanced, the payment system and manner of promotion should be polished and the complexity of the system for online donations should be kept to a minimum.

The initial UTAUT model doesn't take sense of trust into account. However, have a major influence on the donor behaviour. According to our research, people are far more probable to make online donations when they have faith in the platform, the project's creator, and the initiative itself. Therefore, the demand for confidence on the part of the potential contributor must be met in order to persuade the public to pay more attention to online philanthropic crowdfunding.

Managerial Implications

The success of these campaigns will ultimately depend on how well crowdfunding platforms can understand the influence of donors and public interest in participating in donation-based campaigns. With the help of this study, they may be able to more accurately classify contributors and fundraisers and choose the best target demographic for each campaign. Donation-based crowdfunding might be useful for persons or organisations that are unable to offer anything in return for the contribution received.

Limitations:

The sample used in this study focuses on crowdfunding initiatives with a donation-based model. It is yet to be observed that if any differences exist between the actual and potential donations at various campaigns. Furthermore, the sample size is small; nevertheless, we hope to increase it through further research.

Internet-based donation-based crowdfunding is currently gaining popularity all around the world, but especially in developing nations. Donors, whether they be individuals, groups or organisations, quietly transform society. Those wishing to encourage the growth of philanthropic crowdfunding can use the conclusions reached by this study. The intentions and actions of people in relation to joining charitable organizations and participating in public welfare initiatives could be further examined based on these findings.

Author Note

Meghana C and Dr. Chandrakala G contributed to the development of this work. Meghana C was responsible for conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, software, validation, and drafting the original manuscript. Dr. Chandrakala G supervised the project, managed administration tasks, and contributed to the conceptualization and review and editing of the manuscript.

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